

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Dec, 2022 | Peer-Reviewed Journal
ISSN 27649733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10965925

THE DIFFICULT GOODBYE OF THE GHOSTWRITER: REFLECTIONS ON THE PRACTICE AND UNDERSTANDING OF THE BRAZILIAN JUDICIARY

AUTHORS

- Péricles Queiroz Araújo
apericles72@gmail.com
- Poliana Freitas Vieira de Araújo

ABSTRACT

In this study, the figure of the ghostwriter, also known in Brazil as “ghost writer”, is presented, as well as his work and the general peculiarities of his literary performance. As it turns out, far beyond a professional who has improved qualities in writing, this author, in most cases, is not even mentioned. He is behind the works, accompanying the development of the success that could have been his. In some cases, the “artistic ego” does not let him accept the forced separation, despite being aware of the clauses of the contract he signed with his client. The forced and distant view of unattainable success must not be easy, to some extent distressing, and it is not uncommon to end up in the Brazilian Courts. The practice of the ghostwriter is a long-standing reality in the production of literature, despite apparently being outside the scope of copyright protection.